

Future Oriented Collaborative Policy
Development for Rural Areas and People

POLIRURAL Foresight Guide to Deep Dives

Impact of COVID-19 on Rural Regions

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Table of Contents

Overview of the Regional Foresight Process	4
PHASE I The Pre-Foresight or Preparatory Phase.....	4
PHASE II The Foresight Proper	5
Expected Outputs of the Deep Dive Exercise	6
Contribution to the Overall Regional Foresight Exercise	7
For Ad-Hoc Opportunities to Influence Regional Policy.....	7
For On-Going European Commission Consultation Processes	8
Deep Dive Methodology	8
Determine the Scope of the Exercise	9
Determine the Complexity of the Exercise.....	9
Involve Relevant Stakeholders, Experts and Policy Actors.....	10
Strategic Conversation Starters	10
Readiness and Preparedness for the Disruption.....	10
Readiness and Preparedness for the Recovery	11
Impact of the Pandemic on Daily-Life and the Health of Individuals	11
Impact on Public Services.....	12
Impact on Work.....	12
Impact on Employment.....	13
Impact on Personal Budgets and Household Incomes.....	13
Impact on Sectors.....	14
Impact on Businesses, Cooperatives, and the Self-employed.....	15
Temporary, Permanent and Structural Change Wrought by the Pandemic	15
Feedback on Use of the Text Mining Tool	16

Overview of the Regional Foresight Process

In the POLIRURAL project, the Foresight process proceeds in three phases. These correspond roughly but not exactly to WP4-6 of the project DoW. The three phases are as follows.

PHASE I The Pre-Foresight or Preparatory Phase

This is when initial goals are set, sponsors are brought on board and the overall scope is decided. It consists mainly of desk-work and one-on-one meetings with key stakeholders. This work will provide clarity on

- The general challenge or challenges to be addressed,
- The overall ambition and expected impact of the initiative,
- The timeline for completion.

Ideally, this is where the core team is assembled, and key stakeholders identified. For convenience we have divided the stakeholders into two main groups:

- The actors, those who make policy at regional level, and provide inputs to those who make policy at national and EU level. Those who design and implement programs and mobilize the budgets and funding needed for their implementation.
- The beneficiaries, those who will benefit from those programs the from the measures that will be implemented on the basis of the vision, action plan and roadmap that will be produced through the Foresight process, the so called “package.”

The work of this phase of the exercise consists of many practical tasks that the core team will have to take on board. Tasks that will help the core team to

- Understand the region, gathering previous studies, visions, policy initiatives,
- Identify key beneficiaries through their representative bodies, bringing them on board,
- Identify key ‘actors’ who will ensure the execution of recommendations,
- Identify key policy events including deadlines for inputs to programming processes,
- Establish the initial ambition or goal of the Foresight initiative,
- Establish an initial implementation plan.

In the course of carrying out this work, the core team will assemble or create important documents that will help them to launch and support the next stage of the work, phase II. These include...

- A Statement of Purpose,
- A list of stakeholders,
- A Foresight process or implementation plan,
- Various background documents such as previous regional Foresight or strategy reports,
- Other documents such as discussion papers, briefing notes and memos.

PHASE II The Foresight Proper

The work of Phase II will inevitably involve more desk work, but it is mainly a social process of engagement with stakeholders. Initially this tends to focus on the organisation of structured encounters with beneficiaries to develop deeper understanding of

- The reality they face,
- The challenges they experience now,
- The challenges they will face in the future,
- The priority needs for action,
- The policy options and measures that might help to achieve a preferred future,
- The possibility for action by public administration to make them happen.

The core team has to organize this work with a view to developing the main documentary outputs of the Foresight initiative, that is the “page” consisting of

- A **VISION** that adequately and usefully describes the region that the beneficiaries would like to live in at some time in the future (the landing point)
- An **ACTION PLAN** that lists the measures that must be implemented in order to achieve that vision,
- A **ROADMAP** that describes the sequencing of those measures, the key indicators, and targets to be achieved as well as the actors in public administration who will have to make sure they happen.

A successful Foresight process will result in the “package” being **ENDORSED** by the main organisations and associations that represent the beneficiaries in the region and **ADOPTED** by key people in public administration.

A well-designed package will include measures for monitoring progress and structures such as monitoring committees to make sure that the public administration does its job and makes sure that the measures get funded and implemented.

This phase starts with a “divergent thinking” approach, where judgement is suspended, minds are expanded, and lessons are learned by looking outside the region to get clues as to how the future will unfold. Then it moves into a “convergent thinking” where options are weighed, collective decisions are made, priorities are set, and the overall outcome is expressed as a shared vision, roadmap, and action plan.

Getting there may involve a series of steps such as:

- Needs Analysis using basic tools such as SWOT, surveys, and trend analysis.
- Drivers’ Analysis to arrive at a shared understanding of what is driving change, how it happens, and how it can be managed from a regional perspective.
- Deep Dives on key challenges to understand their nature and impact on the region,
- Setting of priorities based on understanding what is important,
- Crystalizing those ideas in the vision, action plan and roadmap.

Needs Analysis has already been dealt with in WP4 of this project. Drivers' Analysis has been supported by the production of the "STEEPV Inventory of Global Drivers of Change." Many of the POLIRURAL Foresight teams are in the process of implementing their Drivers' Analysis. The next step is the implementation of Deep Dives on priority issues. We will now provide guidance on the organization and implementation of Deep Dives on a limited number of issues of potential importance to all pilots, namely the impact of COVID, the Green Deal, CAP Reform and Biodiversity.

Expected Outputs of the Deep Dive Exercise

COVID-19 has radically disrupted life for most people. But it should not have come as a surprise. Experts have warned of the threat of such a pandemic for many years. Yet few countries or regions put in place systems to help them deal with such a crisis when it might happen, how to save both lives and livelihoods, and fewer still knew what to do to recover to a new normal, from the havoc it could wreak.

We have not yet come through the crisis of COVID-19, but one year on from when the first lockdowns were announced we should be able to learn from what has happened and better prepare for the next crisis when it occurs.

For reasons, which include climate change and an increasingly crowded planet, it is likely that we will have to endure similar crises in future. Not only pandemic crises that directly affect human health, but crises that put our food system in jeopardy by attacking crops, or crises caused by increased inequality, poverty, migration, or shortages of essential raw materials.

In 2020, building upon its experience of the COVID crisis, in particular on the disruption caused throughout its global supply chain, Unilever released its new strategy for the future, intended to make it more resilient in the face of such a crisis and more agile in its response. An important element of this strategy was the anticipation of future shocks to its system. The following diagram is a warning that the disruption caused by COVID is not the biggest disruption that we will face, that far bigger threats are coming our way, and that we need to learn from the experience of COVID to prepare for what is to come.

The key concept in this context is RESILIENCE. The concept is not new. For many years now it has been used to “nuance” calls for companies, countries, and regions to become and act more sustainably.

The new policy goal is to achieve a higher level of resilience, one that will help regions better prepare for and react to major disruptions, better preserve lives and livelihoods while we live through its consequences and emerge in good shape when it passes to reach new and better levels of well-being and prosperity.

A Deep-Dive into the impact of COVID in your region is a good place to start to understand the challenge that a crisis like COVID represents, evaluate how well your region responded to the event, how it will be changed as a result, what need to be done to recover, and what needs to be done to be ready for when the next crisis occurs.

Contribution to the Overall Regional Foresight Exercise

Every region of the POLIRURAL project has been affected by COVID. So almost any strategic exercise conducted at regional level in this period must refer to the impact of COVID and factor in “lessons learned” from the last year in any new vision of the future.

Some of the impacts will be negative, some will be positive? Many of them will not be new in that they correspond to an acceleration of trends that were already underway.

The scope for direct action by regional authorities will differ from one region to another, based on the degree of decentralization and the relationship that region has with its national administrative capital.

Each of the POLIRURAL project will therefore have to see for itself by what means its needs can be made known, and by what means its action plan can be implemented. The starting point in any case is an honest appraisal of the impact of COVID-19 in that region and of the measures needed to assure its recovery.

For Ad-Hoc Opportunities to Influence Regional Policy

There may be other opportunities to provide policy inputs on issues related to the COVID-19 and the broader issue of achieving resilience. The European Commission has ear-marked about €750B to help EU member states deal with the impact of the pandemic. Together with other elements of the EU budget, foreseen before the pandemic, this comes to a €1.8T recovery fund, to be spent between now and 2027. It is up to the member states to create their own COVID recovery action plan and negotiate with the how much they will draw down and under what conditions. More information about the recovery fund including details about what it can be used for are provide here¹.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/recovery-plan-europe_en

Although several plans have been approved by the Commission², there is general dissatisfaction with the quality of the plans proposed so far. In January of this year Euractiv reports³ that the “Commission demands more precision and ambition in national recovery plans.” The member states have until April 2021 to submit their plans and based on the drafts received so far and according to Euractiv the Commission has requested “more specific milestones and targets and more ambitious reforms in their recovery plans .”

There may be an opportunity for pilots to provide concrete proposals that will help their national governments submit better plans. It is up to each pilot to find out who this can be done in their country, perhaps by talking to the right people in your regional administration, their delegation in Brussels, or the EC delegation in your country.

There will be no money without a plan and where there is a plan, it may proceed in phases or it may require revision as the true nature of the challenges to be addressed are understood.

For On-Going European Commission Consultation Processes

The European Commission also requires inputs to its policies and programming cycles. In this case to its policies and programming for regional development, as well as for the COVID recovery. The budget may have been won, but that is only the start of a long processes of making it available and putting it to work.

The work you do in you regional Foresight could have an impact if it is produced in a timely manner.

Deep Dive Methodology

Despite their obvious similarities, each of the 12 teams running regional Foresight initiatives in the POLIRURAL, pursues an independent agenda at its own pace. This is required in order to achieve a result that is relevant, timely and actionable, likely to be endorsed by local power players and adopted by local champions in public administration.

Nevertheless, they have a shared interest in issues that should have a shaping effect on their future path to progress. These issues include

- The regional impact of COVID-19
- The Green Deal
- CAP Reform
- The new biodiversity strategy

We therefore use these four issues as a basis for illustrating the application of the Deep-Dive methodology, as part of the Foresight process.

² <https://www.politico.eu/tag/national-recovery-plans/>

³ <https://www.euractiv.com/section/economy-jobs/news/commission-demands-more-precision-and-ambition-in-national-recovery-plans/>

There are natural links between the four issues and regional teams might pick and ix from the lists of conversation starters or introduce new material as appropriate. Hopefully these four examples will provide sufficient illustration of the method and its application, to enable the team to develop their own material as support for any other subject they might decide to address.

Determine the Scope of the Exercise

Different regions may choose to emphasis different aspects of how COVID has impacted their region. Some regions may focus on disruption to business or employment, others may focus on how it has affected specific sectors such as tourism or farming, whereas others might prefer to focus on how it has affected overall quality of life. Some regions might decide to tackle all of these issues. In any case it may make sense to limit the scope in some way, based on priorities for regional growth and development.

The first task of the regional team will be to determine the scope of the deep-dive. As preparation for a deep-dive exercise on the impact of COVID, we have prepared a series of questions under several headings. The regional team will decide if it wants to use all or only some of these lists of conversation starters. In choosing those questions we have tried to be exhaustive, but it is possible that we have omitted something important, and if so the user of this guide is invited to develop their own lists to fill in any gaps that may appear.

There are many ways to do this. It can be a simple choice taken unilaterally by the core team, the result of discussions with a limited number of key stakeholders, or the result of a consultation with a broader selection of stakeholders.

Determine the Complexity of the Exercise

It is impossible and arguably unwise to prescribe in too much detail how each region should do their work. The best we can do is to flag some of he issues that they will have to manage as the organizers and social engineers of these participative policy events.

Each region faces practical constraints in terms of available time and looming deadlines for actionable results, or limited resources available for the core team. For those and other reasons, it is important to design the exercise so that useful will be gathered and summarized in a report that can be circulated afterwards, to be validated by those who could not take part.

The core team will have to decide how the work will be organized. If it will consist of a mixture of online and physical events. It is will involve plenary or break-out events, all held on the same day or spread out over several days. Each session requires careful planning to make sur that the right people show up and take part, that adequate documentation is provided in advance, that the sessions are well managed and that reporting on the sessions is carried out by skilled reporters, that will do justice to those who take part. The core team might decide to record sessions and make the recordings available afterwards long with slides-decks and background papers, for those who could not take part.

In the case of the POLIRURAL project, we hope to make use of the Text mining tools developed within the project to support the preparation of briefing notes and background papers.

Involve Relevant Stakeholders, Experts and Policy Actors

One of the challenges that each core team will face is the challenge of moving beyond anecdote to actionable intelligence. Anecdotes are very important. They allow the core team to formulate hypotheses about the reality of what is going on. They help the core team to formulate specific questions for experts to reflect upon. Ideally these experts will take part in the meetings, will engage with the stakeholders who may argue from their lived experience, and offer opinions and views based on their expertise and experience.

Ideally these experts should be informed in advance about the issues to be discussed. They may provide links to background documents that can be distributed in advance and they may be invited to make presentations or short speeches to anchor the discussions in what is known about the subject matter and guide discussions towards conclusions that are robust and authoritative being based on the best evidence available. Sometimes that evidence is not available. This is not failure of the process, just the discovery of questions which may be of great importance for the region, and which may require further study, research or data-gathering before a solid position can be formulated. In this situation it may not be possible to formulate measures to address the situation. But it may be possible to suggest measures such as the funding of the studies needed to decide.

It is part of the work of the core team to make sure that different parts of this work is adequately served by relevant stakeholders who can share their experience of what is going on, but also that it is adequately served by experts that will enrich the exercise based on their science, what they know from the literature, and what they know from on-going discussions with their peers who may be living elsewhere.

Strategic Conversation Starters

What follows is a series of questions that you might use to motivate discussions about the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on your region, how well the region responded, what it needs to do for a full recovery, and how it might respond better to the next crisis. You can think of them as conversation starters.

It is inevitable that lists such as these are incomplete or leave out something important. So, use any, all or none of these as you see fit. Extend, amend, or improve these questions in any way you see fit.

Readiness and Preparedness for the Disruption

The possibility of a pandemic such as the COVID-19 pandemic has been known for a long time. Right now we are busy coping with COVID-19. It is worth noting that pandemics occur throughout the world on a regular basis and they will occur again in your region. Some of them affect people, others affect livestock and others affect plants including plants of commercial value for food and agriculture, forestry, and related industries. So

it is a good time to take stock and decide how to better prepare for the next time such large-scale disruption occurs.

The first “adult” conversation a region might choose to have relates to its readiness for this crisis, the speed with which it was able to react, and the effectiveness of this reaction. The reason for having this conversation is to determine what should be done in order to react better and more effectively the next time such a crisis occurs.

- Was the region prepared for this pandemic?
- Did it react quickly enough?
- Were the measures taken adequate?
- What must be done to be better prepared the next time, not just for pandemics such as COVID but for any other disruption that might occur?

Readiness and Preparedness for the Recovery

The Pandemic has had a very high impact on the lives of those living in the region, as well as on the lives of their friends, relatives, clients, customers and business partners in neighbouring and otherwise related regions. For many businesses and individuals it has exhausted their financial reserves and their ability to bounce back afterwards, when people can travel and mix more freely, and life returns to a new normal.

The EC has boosted its budget for the period 2021-2027 by €750B bringing it to a total of €1.85T. The extra money is the COVID recovery fund. Much of this will be spent on initiatives related to the Green Deal. This is expected to lead to the creation of new jobs, in particular in areas such as building renovation. These will help to replace jobs lost through the pandemic. So it is useful to ask...

- Does your region, business leaders, civic leaders and those who work in public administration, know what to do in the recovery?
- Is there a plan to follow-up on the recovery fund?
- How can this regional Foresight process contribute to regional readiness for the recovery?

Impact of the Pandemic on Daily-Life and the Health of Individuals

It is useful to take stock of the toll of the pandemic on the regional population and get an idea of the scale of the task of recovery. A good starting point is to gather the basic numbers:

- How many people have been infected?
- How many people died?
- How many lockdowns have you endured?
- What is the overall trend?
- Is there an end in sight?
- When will everyone be vaccinated?
- When will things return to normal?

Impact on Public Services

Arguably, those working in public administration have been the best protected from the worst effects of the pandemic. But it is no longer true that all of those working in the public sector benefit from good pay, good pensions, and generous working conditions. Many are on short term contracts with fewer rights than many of their (usually older) colleagues. This is especially true in sectors such as education, where many are on short term contracts where they work 9 months a year and who up in September in the hope of getting teaching hours. Those who work in personal care are often employed via placement agencies. Nurses and doctors too often work under poor conditions. So it can be expected that some public services will degrade in a situation such as the pandemic. There are reports of the negative impact of a degradation in teaching and learning, and its impact on the education, career prospects and even the mental health of young people. There are reports of people forgoing important medical interventions (such as cancer diagnosis) and suffering unnecessarily as a result. Once again, every region is different. It might be useful to arrive at an assessment of the situation by looking in detail at the experience of the public in areas such as:

- Education
- Healthcare
- Care of the elderly and vulnerable groups
- Police and emergency services
- Transport

Impact on Work

There is evidence that the pandemic has caused severe hardship for many groups of people. It is said that women in particular have been hard hit. Especially those who now WFH, and can no longer put their kids in crèche, essential workers juggling fewer opportunities to shop and degraded or discontinued personal service. There is evidence that the pandemic has increased social inequalities and accelerated negative trends that had already been established before the pandemic struck.

- How many now work from home (WFH)?
- How is that working out?
- For example, are homes big enough to accommodate working adults and studying children?
- Is bandwidth adequate to accommodate large numbers working all day?
- How many now work remotely from a co-working space?
- Are these spaces adequately equipped for remote work?
- What is the impact on children and children's education?
- What is the impact on household budgets?
- Was it necessary to purchase new furniture, IT, and storage space?
- Has it led to higher energy costs (extra heating and IT due to WFH)?
- How has this been reflected in the incidence of domestic violence, anxiety, stress, suicide?

- Has there been an increase in crime, in theft, burglary, drugs or random violence?
- How has this been reflected in physical health due to lack of exercise, closure of gyms?
- How has the burden of work changed for specific groups such as mothers with young children, single mothers, families with teenagers, people who are unemployed or in search of work, households with essential workers, gig workers, people on zero-hour contracts?
- What is the upside of WFH?
- What is the downside of WFH?

Impact on Employment

Different sectors will have been affected in different ways. Some sectors such as HORECA, tourism, travel, and leisure, have been devastated. Crops have not been harvested due to lack of seasonal labourers, unable to travel. Food processing factories have been closed down due to poor working conditions that facilitate the spread of disease. Others have even benefited. There is evidence that 2020 was a good year for European venture capital and that many technology-based businesses, perhaps better suited to WFH, have been hiring. But this will play out differently in different regions. Each region needs to independently master the details of its own situation.

- What sectors have been affected?
- How many jobs have been lost?
- How many people on furlough?
- How likely are these to become layoffs?
- How many layoffs are likely to become permanent?
- What are the ages of those being laid-off?
- What are the prospects of their getting their jobs back?
- What are the prospects of their finding new work?
- What about the quality of new work?
- What differences for full-time, part-time, out-of-region and seasonal / migrant workers?
- How has this affected salaries?
- Some employees may feel that the worker who now commutes less, needs less salary to cover the cost of commuting. Some employees may feel that since workers can live further from the place of work, they can find lower cost places to live and no longer need “high” salaries to cover their high cost of living. So, how has WFH affected salaries and benefits?

Impact on Personal Budgets and Household Incomes

Many have been furloughed or laid off, or their businesses have failed. Many have had to endure significant reductions in income. Those who relied on informal work will have been hit very hard, as they may have been excluded from most forms of relief or income support.

- How many have difficulty paying bills?
- How many people have difficulty paying rent?
- How many have had their homes or other assets possessed by creditors?
- How many have been evicted?
- How many were made homeless?
- How many have been rehoused in appropriate accommodation?
- How have these changes affected the price of property?
- How have these changes affected the available-of residential, commercial property?
- How have these changes affected the availability of farmland?
- How many have benefited from relief schemes?
- Are these schemes adequate and fair?
- How were they funded?
- When will they be discontinued?
- Will the beneficiaries one day have to pay-off deferred rents or other debts?
- Will they be able to afford that?
- If not, what will happen then?

Impact on Sectors

In terms of revenues, reserves, suppliers, employees...

- Which sectors have been affected negatively?
- Which sectors have been affected positively?

On a sector-by-sector basis what do you know about

- Retail?
- Restaurants and cafés?
- Leisure and entertainment (sports, concerts, cinemas, festivals, galleries, museums...)?
- Long-distance travel (by plane, international train, boat ...)?
- Local travel (local trains, metro, bus, taxi...)?
- Hotels and accommodation?
- Agriculture and food processing?
- Manufacturing?
- Construction?
- IT?
- Other?

Impact on Businesses, Cooperatives, and the Self-employed

From a business owner's perspective, the impact has been significant. Not all businesses have deep pockets and vast reserves of cash with which to wait out a crisis. Many small business are mom-and-pop affairs that rely on footfall and customers having money to spend locally. Many rely on clients from which they get "orders". Many of these may have only one large client on whom they depend critically for the lion's share of their revenues. Some of these are social enterprises.

They may depend on philanthropy and volunteering.

- How has the pandemic affected revenues?
- How many have had to lay off workers, down-grade them or reduce their salaries?
- How many have shut temporarily?
- How many have shut permanently?
- How many have benefited from relief programs?
- Where did the money for this come from?
- What happens when this money is spent?
- Do they have to pay it back?
- Will they be able to pay it back?

Temporary, Permanent and Structural Change Wrought by the Pandemic

For those who study trends, it is clear that many of the changes wrought by COVID are changes that had already started to happen. The role of COVID has been to accelerate those change. WFH is a good example. So is the move by certain groups from cities to the countryside. So is the adoption of e-commerce and practice such as home delivery of retail it is likely that those accelerated transformations will be permanent and will not return to a pre-pandemic normal. But other changes will be fleeting. So, it is important to talk about the nature of the changes you observe in your region, as the answer to the following questions will have an important impact on how you see the future, how you formulate your regional vision of a desirable future, and how you prioritize what needs to be done to achieve it.

- What changes have happened?
- What changes are probably only temporary?
- What changes may be permanent?
- What changes are structural?
- What changes provide an opportunity to make improvements and build back better?
- What needs to be done to lock in the positive changes and take advantage of opportunities?

One already established trend that has accelerated due to COVID and that has bene enabled by WFH is the movement of professionals, business, and start-up owners to rural areas to avoid high cost of city living. That trend merits a conversation of its own!

Feedback on Use of the Text Mining Tool

Just as for any other part of the Foresight process, a successful Deep-Dive requires adequate preparation. Typically, this includes the provision of briefing notes and background documents in advance of the meeting, to get everyone thinking about issues and gather the thoughts and positions that they will bring to the interactive sessions that represent such an important part of the exercise.

The selection and provision of such material in a suitable format, accessible to the broad range of stakeholders that is usually involved in the Foresight process, requires considerable effort on the part of the core team.

Normally, this kind of work is done “by hand” often by someone with a research background who has access to literature, is able to read and understand vast amounts of related documentation, is able to select those that are most relevant and insightful, and then makes short summary texts explaining the key points and why they are relevant to the issue at hand.

I refer to these summary texts as “curated reading lists” in the sense that their creation requires the selection of relevant texts, whose references are provided along with a summary of the main points and their relevance.

The members of the core team will still have to make a selection, and they may be helped in this by the browsing and visualization tools included in the semex.io toolkit, but the toolkit also contains a tool to help in the production of the curated reading lists. Our hope is that this will prove a useful and labor-saving device in the context of the work of the core teams.

It is unlikely that the core teams can rely on those tools to carry out the bulk of their work, as they are still in an early stage of development. Nevertheless, it is expected that all regional teams will use the occasion of their deep-dive exercises as opportunities to test out those tools and provide feedback on their potential for economies of effort.

In particular it is expected that each team will use...

- The data-visualization and browsing tools to help in the selection of relevant documents,
- The CRL tool to create memos and back-ground documents to support their deep-dive processes.

It is expected that the core teams will provide feedback on the use of these tools in terms of...

- Their usefulness or potential usefulness,
- The labor saved or potential for labor-savings,
- The performance of the tools with English and non-English language sources,
- Ways in which the tools could be improved,
- Any other comments or remarks that come to mind.

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